

Clinical Utility of Homoeopathic Remedies under the *Solanaceae* Family for the Treatment of Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease

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ABSTRACT:

The homoeopathic remedy under the Solanaceae family, has been extensively used to treat Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD). However, scientific research conclusively proving its utility is lacking. This study was performed to ascertain the remedy's therapeutic utility and efficacy in treating Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease and its complications using the COPD Assessment Test (CAT). A prospective uncontrolled observational study with purposive sampling was performed; the subjects were selected from the outpatient department. A total of 30 cases, fulfilling the inclusion and exclusion criteria were clinically examined. The CAT score was noted before and after treatment with indicated remedy under the Solanaceae Family were performed. The Paired T-test was applied and the change in the median CAT was found to be statistically significant. P-value of the CAT score before Treatment was 20.37 ± 3.02 and that of the CAT score after treatment was 11.30 ± 5.90 with a mean change of 9.07 ± 2.88 and 37.69% improvement with P-value of $0.000 < 0.01$.

KEYWORDS: COPD, *Solanaceae* family, Homoeopathy, CAT, Antioxidant

INTRODUCTION:

COPD is a poorly reversible disease of the lungs that is one of the major causes of morbidity worldwide. In the United States, it's the fourth leading cause of death after heart complaint, cancer, and cerebrovascular complaint. By 2020, it's projected to come the third leading cause of death worldwide[3]. Tamil Nadu has 4000 cases of COPD per one lakh population, and occupies the 17th rank in terms of frequency in the country. In India, the incidence is around 15% in children [3]. The prevalence ranged between 2 to 22% among the men and 1.2 to 19% among women in different population-based studies across India. [9]

The DALY rates were significantly higher in the Empowered Action Group (EAG) states including Bihar, Jharkhand, Chattisgarh, etc. Also, COPD ranked the seventh among the North-East states [20].

COPD is a group of pathological conditions in which there is chronic, partial or complete, obstruction to the airflow at any level from trachea to the smallest airways resulting in functional disability of the lungs. Symptoms include cough, wheezing, breathlessness and chest tightness [20]. Chronic inflammation and increased oxidative stress occurs in the lungs and systemically in COPD. Oxidative stress plays a vital role in the pathogenesis of COPD, including oxidative inactivation of antiproteases and surfactants, mucus hypersecretion, membrane lipid peroxidation, alveolar epithelial injury, remodeling of extracellular matrix, and apoptosis.

A study evaluated the antioxidant property in the drugs belonging to *Solanaceae* family where, *S. Dulcamara* had the highest antioxidant activity [21]. The drugs belonging to *Solanaceae* family are not only botanically similar but they are also similar in their medicinal action. All the plants of this family possess the alkaloid atropine and also possess mydriatic qualities [16].

Oxidative stress is said to be the major pathology in COPD and therefore, targeting oxidative stress with antioxidants or boosting the endogenous levels of antioxidants is likely to be beneficial in the treatment of COPD. Hence, the objective of the present study is to targeted the local lung and systemic oxidative stress with the drugs under the *Solanaceae* family that modulate the antioxidants/redox system or boost endogenous antioxidants which would be a useful therapeutic approach in COPD.

METHODS:

The study was a prospective observational case study with no control group taken to prevent ethical pitfalls regarding patients not on any treatment. The study was performed following the protocol laid down in the 1964 Declaration of Helsinki. The subjects for the study were selected using purposive sampling, from the patients who reported to the Outpatient Department of G.D. Memorial Homoeopathic Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India. The inclusion criteria were age group between 16 and 60 years and patients who were diagnosed with mild to moderate Grade of COPD. Patients who were having severe COPD and any other respiratory illness were excluded in the study. All the patients were screened for COPD, and assessed using the CAT tool. It is standard tool in all COPD and is usually correlated with the severity of the COPD. The subjects included in the screening were assessed using CAT tool and score were noted before and after treatment. A total of 65

subjects who fulfilled the inclusion criteria were initially enrolled for the study for the duration of 6 months. The patients who continued the treatment protocol for 3 months after initial consultation were considered for final analysis. The baseline score and the final score after 3 months were used for analysis.

All patients were made aware about the study and its procedures. A written consent was obtained from each patient. Their cases were defined using a Standardized Case Record with CAT score forms. Finally, 30 patients completed the study and comprised the sample. The remedy under the *Solanaceae* family was selected after proper Repertorisation and the potency was selected based on the susceptibility of the patient. Indicated Remedy under *Solanaceae* family was administered orally twice a day for 3 months to all the patients half an hour before food. The patients were followed up every 2 weeks once and depending upon the condition of the patient. The repetition of twice daily was made considering the principles of homoeopathic posology as well as the state and stage of disease, susceptibility of patient, and symptom similarity. The data collected were analyzed and summarized using frequency, percentage, and mean and standard deviation. The significance was assessed using the Paired T-test and Chi-square test.

RESULTS:

In our study, the CAT tool was useful to study the changes in the clinical scores; we could efficiently validate the changes in the clinical presentation and the evolving remedy responses. In our study of patients with COPD the number percentage of male patients were 57% and the number percentage of females were 43%. [Figure:1]. Dust is the most common cause for COPD which was observed during this study. The number percentage of exposed to dust were 50%, the number percentage of cold air exposure were 36.67% and the number of cases due to cold foods were 13.33%[Table: 1]. The cases presented with Bronchial asthma were ($n=19$, 63.33%) and Chronic Bronchitis were ($n=11$, 36.67%)[Table: 2]. Improvement of the cases of COPD with Belladonna were ($n=7$, 23.33%), Stramonium were ($n=4$, 13.33%), Capsicum were ($n=4$, 13.33%) which were frequently used remedies under the *Solanaceae* family[Figure: 4]. Jamovi software was used for statistical evaluation. The Paired T-test was applied and the change in the median CAT was found to be statistically significant. P -value of the CAT score before Treatment was 20.37 ± 3.02 and that of the CAT score after treatment was 11.30 ± 5.90 [Table:3]. The mean change of 9.07 ± 2.88 indicating the improvement (P -value of $0.000 < 0.01$).

Figure 1: Distribution of Cases according to Gender**Table 1: Distribution of cases based on CAUSE**

CAUSE	Counts	% of Total	Cumulative %
COLD AIR EXPOSURE	11	36.67%	36.67%
COLD FOODS	4	13.33%	50.00%
DUST	15	50.00%	100.00%

Table 2: Distribution of cases based on DIAGNOSIS

DIAGNOSIS	Counts	% of Total	Cumulative %
BRONCHIAL ASTHMA	19	63.33 %	63.33 %
CHRONIC BRONCHITIS	11	36.67 %	100.00%

Figure 2: Distribution of Diagnosis based on the Gender

Figure 3: Distribution of Diagnosis based on the Causative Factor

Figure 4: Frequencies of Medicines used based on the Diagnosis

Figure 5: Distribution of Improvement based on the Medicines

Table 3: Paired T-Test Value of the effect of the Medicine against the COPD before and after treatment

	N	Mean	SE	Median	SD
CAT BT	30	20.37	0.5519	20.500	3.023
CAT AT	30	11.30	1.0787	9.000	5.908

Table 4: Paired T-Test Value of the effect of the Medicine against the COPD before and after treatment

	Statistic	df	p	Mean difference	SE difference
CAT	7.669	29.00	< .001	9.067	1.182

DISCUSSION:

The various studies have shown that homoeopathic treatment was very successful in the treatment of COPD. This study was done to confirm the same. As this is an observational study, results were obtained very quickly and there was also no risk of loss to follow up of patients. The frequently indicated homoeopathic remedies prescribed in cases of Bronchial Asthma and Chronic Bronchitis under the *Solanaceae* family were found out[Figure: 4] and this will help in treatment of more such cases. However, there were also a few limitations of this study – the sample size was small and no patient with diagnosis of Emphysema, Bronchiectasis and small Airway disease were included in the study.

CONCLUSION:

From the present study, we can conclude that Medicines under *Solanaceae* family were effective in the management of COPD and its complications, based on the significant improvement in the CAT after treatment. From this study, it is inferred that, the remedies prescribed after repertorisation includes Belladonna, Capsicum, Dulcamara, Hyoscyamus, Stramonium, Tabacum and the frequently prescribed remedies in this study were Belladonna and Stramonium[Figure: 4]. In future, studies with larger population and longer follow-up duration are required to produce more in-depth and useful data.

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DECLARATION OF PATIENT CONSENT:

We have obtained appropriate consent from the patient.

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CONFLICTS OF INTEREST:

There are no conflicts of interest.

ETHICAL APPROVAL:

The study was approved by the Institutional Ethics Committee. The study was performed following the protocol laid down in the 1964 Declaration of Helsinki.

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